

Amperometric Estimation of Copper with Ortho-hydroxy Acetophenone Oxime

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Ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime has been successfully used as a reagent for the amperometric titration of copper (II) (0.26 mM to 4.2 mM) using sodium acetate-acetic acid mixture as the supporting electrolyte cum buffer (*pH* 4.6). A compact manual polarographic set complete with potentiometer and a suitable spot-reflecting galvanometer as a current measuring device has been made use of in carrying out these titrations. Direct titrations of copper in the presence of appreciable amounts of foreign metal ions like Zn^{++} , Mn^{++} , Cd^{++} , Pb^{++} , Mg^{++} and Ni^{++} have proved quite satisfactory. Results of estimation of copper by this method in a sample of leaded brass have also been shown.

The potentiality of ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime as an analytical reagent for the gravimetric estimation of copper has already been established by Poddar¹. It has been observed that copper in solution is completely precipitated by this reagent between *pH*, 2.1 and 8.0, forming a compound of the composition $Cu(C_8H_8O_2N)_2$. The present paper deals with the development of a suitable method for utilizing this reagent in the amperometric titration of copper. A buffer solution containing 0.1 *M* sodium acetate and 0.1 *M* acetic acid (*pH* 4.6) has been found to be the most appropriate medium for conducting the titrations in which copper is quantitatively precipitated by this reagent. The titrations are best carried out at a potential of -0.6 volt vs S.C.E. using a dropping mercury electrode at which the diffusion current due to the reaction $Cu(II) \rightarrow Cu(O)$ is fully developed whereas the reagent itself undergoes very little change. 0.5 mg to 8.0 mg copper in solutions at very low concentrations (0.26 mM to 4.2 mM) can be easily determined with sufficient accuracy using a simple manual polarograph assembly. The presence of a little gelatin (0.005%) in the titrating solution serves as the maximum suppressor. Titrations of copper have also been conducted in presence of a number of foreign metal ions like zinc, manganese, cadmium, lead, magnesium and nickel with good results without any interference from these metals. Estimation of copper in a sample of leaded brass using this titration procedure has also proved quite satisfactory.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amperometric titrations as well as the recording of polarograms were carried out in a manual polarographic set of the conventional type.

Ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime—The reagent was prepared according to the method described earlier² and purified by recrystallisation from ethyl alcohol. 0.1 molar and 0.025 molar solutions of the reagent in aqueous ethanol were used.

1. S. N. Poddar, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **155**, 327.
2. S. N. Poddar, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 254.

Copper (II) solution—A standard copper solution was prepared by dissolving a weighed quantity of electrolytic copper strips. The copper content of the solution was verified by the iodometric method.

Acetate buffer solution (0.2 M)—Anhydrous sodium acetate (16.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (12 ml.) were dissolved in water and made up to 1 litre.

In addition to these two other solutions viz., sodium acetate (0.1 M) and acetic acid (0.5 M) were prepared for using as buffer during titration of copper in presence of nickel.

A freshly prepared 0.5% gelatin solution was used as the maximum suppressor.

All other chemicals and reagents used were of A.R. or G.R. qualities.

Titration Procedure—Appropriate voltage for the titration was selected as usual from a comparison of the polarograms of both the copper and the reagent solutions. From the curves this voltage was found to be—0.6 volt (vs. S.C.E.), at which diffusion current due to the reduction of the cupric ion in solution fully developed while the reagent remains completely unaffected.

For titration purpose, a set of copper solutions were prepared from calculated amounts of the standard copper solution, acetate buffer solution and 0.5% gelatin solution. Each of these copper solutions were 0.1 molar in both sodium acetate and acetic acid containing 0.005% gelatin as the maximum suppressor and the pH values were around 4.6.

An aliquot portion (30 ml.) of any of these copper solutions was transferred to the titration cell, deaerated with a stream of pure hydrogen and then titrated at—0.6v (vs. S.C.E.) with appropriate concentration of the standard reagent solution taken in a microburette following the usual procedure. The end point was accurately determined by the graphical method from the point of intersection of the two straight line portions of an L-shaped curve [Fig. 1] obtained by plotting the galvanometer deflections (current values) against the volume of the reagent added applying the usual volume corrections to account for the dilution effect of the titrating solution.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Amperometric titration curve of copper with *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime.

All the titrations were carried out at the room temperature (30°C). Copper concentrations from 8 mg–2 mg were titrated with 0.1 molar reagent solution while those from 1 mg–0.5 mg with 0.025 molar reagent solution. The results of these titrations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Amperometric titration of copper with ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime

Volume of Solution titrated V ₁ (ml)	Copper		Error (%)
	Present (mg)	Found (mg)	
30	8.4	8.4	0.00
30	6.3	6.28	-0.30
30	5.25	5.22	-0.58
30	4.22	4.22	0.00
30	2.10	2.10	0.00
30	1.05	1.05	0.00
30	0.525	0.527	+0.30

Titrations in presence of diverse metal ions : Copper titrations were also successfully carried out in presence of appreciable amounts of interfering metallic ions like zinc, manganese, cadmium, lead, magnesium and nickel without any difficulty. Copper solutions for titrations in presence of the first five elements were prepared in the manner already described. But for titration in presence of nickel, however, the concentrations of sodium acetate and acetic acid in the copper solution had to be adjusted to 0.06 molar and 0.35 molar respectively to lower the pH of the titrating mixture to about 4.0 as nickel is precipitated by the reagent at pH 4.5. The titration procedure was similar to that described earlier. Some of the results of these titrations are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

Titration of copper in presence of other metals

Foreign metals present (mg)	Copper		Error (%)
	Present (mg)	Found (mg)	
Zn, 100	2.0	2.0	0.00
Mn, 100	2.0	2.0	0.00
Cd, 100	2.0	2.0	0.00
Pb, 100	2.0	2.0	0.00
Mg, 100	2.0	2.0	0.00
Ni, 100	2.00	2.01	+0.50

Estimation of copper in brass : The above titration procedure was used in the estimation of copper in standard leaded brass with satisfactory results. For this, a solution was made by dissolving accurately weighed amount of standard brass drillings in 4 : 5 nitric acid (sp. gr. 1.2) in the usual manner. The solution was evaporated to dryness on a steam bath and the dried residue was dissolved in water with a few drops of glacial acetic acid and the volume was then made up to 250 ml.

Titration were then carried out with appropriate aliquots of this brass solution following the procedure described for the estimation of Cu in presence of nickel. The results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

Titration of copper in standard brass solution*

Volume of the brass solution titrated (ml)	Copper present (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Error (%)
6	8.00	8.00	0.00
3	4.00	4.00	0.00
4.5	6.00	6.00	0.00
1.5	2.00	2.00	0.00

*Composition of the standard brass sample :

Cu, 70.8% ; Zn, 24.2% ; Sn, 1.85% ; Pb, 2.52% ; Fe, 0.31% ; P, 0.06% ; Mn, 0.12% ; Ni, 0.17% .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in Table I show that ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime can very well be used as a good amperometric reagent for the estimation of small concentrations of copper with accurate results. The method appears to be all the more attractive as accurate results are obtained even in presence of preponderant amounts of a number of interfering metal ions like Zn^{++} , Mn^{++} , Cd^{++} , Mg^{++} , Pb^{++} and Ni^{++} . This is possible because none of these metal ions are affected by the prevailing conditions of the titration. This has been further illustrated by the successful estimation of copper in a sample of standard brass (Table III) where most of these metals are present as subsidiary constituents of the alloy. The titration procedure with this reagent is simple, accurate and quick and has the additional advantage that direct titration of copper is feasible with this reagent whereas similar titrations with its wellknown simpler precursor salicylaldehyde involves indirect titration procedure³.

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3. A. Neuberger, *Arch. Eisenhüttenw.*, 1939, 13, 171.